

An Empirical Research Work on “Work Place Flexibility” under Contemporary Scenario of Secure Closure Situation due to COVID-19 [Corona Virus] in the Spotlight of Organizational Behavior and Human Nature in India.

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Abstract: today, whole world is facing a serious situation where people are afraid from people all over the world the markets are down, manufacturing and other related activities are stopped due to COVID-19 [Corona Virus] attack. People are lockdown in their homes and factories are other marketing activities are totally stopped. The best alternative is to work from home, the “work flexibility” companies are allowing the employees to work from home.

This research paper is spotting the light on the human nature and various aspects of the “work flexibility under this tensed and stressed situation, ideally the “work flexibility” is an option under the normal conditions to give a break to the employee so that he/she can work in a relaxed mood, not bound to the formal dress etc. but in the current situation the employees are tensed and stressed and there is no other option to work from home, in this situation this is a study of human nature and various aspects on the work and productivity in terms of organization behavior .

Keywords: “work flexibility”, work from home, COVID-19, Corona virus, organization behavior, human nature, lockdown, secure closure of people.

I. INTRODUCTION

This research paper is spotting the light on the human nature and various aspects of the “work flexibility under this tensed and stressed situation, ideally the “work flexibility” is an option under the normal conditions to give a break to the employee so that he/she can work in a relaxed mood, not bound to the formal dress etc. but in the current situation the employees are tensed and stressed and there is no other option to work from home, in this situation this is a study of human nature and various aspects on the work and productivity in terms of organization behavior .

In an organization, there is a separate department that deals with the humans and human nature, “Human Resource” department and the behavior is studies under organizational behavior. There are typically two types of customers internal and external, here in this paper the author is concentrating on the internal

customers of an organization. There are many things happening in an organization to ease out the internal customers “the employees” and get their maximum potential for the productivity of an organization. There are incentives, various schemes, assistance in kid’s tuition fee, health insurance and many more in the list.

There is one “incentive” that is known as “work flexibility” where the employees are not bound to come to the office and they can do their assigned work from their home.

Human nature, is never being a satisfied kind of, they always want more, like paid holidays, long weekends etc. now in the current situation caused due to “COVID-19” virus, people are bound at homes and many companies are making arrangements for their external customers to ease out the situation and many employees are working from their homes to help the organization.

In ideal conditions, this can be a relaxation and an advantage to the employees to work from home, and it is. Many companies are giving this option once in the month as per the policy or the company, but in current scenario both companies and employees are bound to face the situation.

There are many sectors where this can be done, like in teaching, meeting at senior level etc. but there are many areas where the online presence is not essentially required but physical presence is a must like in manufacturing sectors where workers are manually doing the work or with the assistance of the automated or semi-automated plant and machinery in assembly line, production etc.

Human intervention cannot be completely replaced in any manufacturing process. There has been complete shutdown in many manufacturing units and noting can be done, the prime objective is to get rid from the corona virus infection.

In this research work the author is concentrating upon the human resource and human nature with special focus on the people who are working from the homes, there are various situation where the work and family conflicts issues can arise, especially for the women employees for this the author is going

to float a serious of question to know the how people behave in this tensed situation.

There has been a loss of billions - millions of dollar in the world and Indian economy, the author is making the effort to give the glimpse of that situation also.

II. COVID-19 AND THE EFFECT ON WORLD ECONOMY AND MARKET

COVID-19 is the official name for the coronavirus disease 2019. The disease is caused by the SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus, which had not previously been identified in humans. The outbreak has been declared a global pandemic: the number of cases has now passed one-and-a-quarter million. There is currently no treatment for the disease, and health systems around the world are becoming overstretched. Pharmaceutical companies and research groups are racing to develop an effective vaccine.

Due to the unique virus there has been a lot of damage in the world's economy and markets. To prevent the massive spread-out as it's a transmissible disease from person to person a worldwide lockdown is announced, as a result of this all the activities are stopped.

Table with 5 columns: as of April 12, 5:00 GMT, Total infections, Active infections, Recoveries, Deaths. Rows include USA, Spain, Italy, France, Germany, China, United Kingdom, Iran, Turkey, Belgium.

Table 1. Showing the impact of COVID-19 Worldwide.

From the above Table [Table 1.] the magnitude of the COVID-19 could be understandable how big the damage is, positive cases and deaths are growing continuously, the author's estimation is the numbers will be increase by the time this paper will be published.

The following image gives the glimpse about the changes in the lifestyle of people due to the sudden change in the situations. Many people and independent organization are trying to find out the reactions and effects of the current situation, as this kind of situation was never happened in the history, even war situation is different in that situation there are people from enemy side but this situation the enemy is within the system of country and stopped all the moving activities.

Changes to the general lifestyle due to the COVID-19 / coronavirus pandemic

Fig. 1. Changes to the general lifestyle due to the COVID-19 / coronavirus pandemic

The above image gives the big picture where world top countries in terms of either population or economy are having the effect.

The following characteristics are came up -

- Stayed at home more
Washed hands more
Applied social distancing
Avoided public places like bars and restaurants
Gone to the shops less
Cancelled plans with family or friends
Travelled less
Cleaned your house more
Shopped online more
Avoided certain shopping times
Avoided public transport
Used less cash
Worked from home
Reduced exercise regime
I have not made any changes to my lifestyle

Similarly there are many concerns and view regarding the COVID-19 spreading all over the worldwide.

Main worries or concerns about the COVID-19 / coronavirus pandemic 2020

Fig. 2. Main worries or concerns about the COVID-19 / coronavirus pandemic 2020

The Main worries or concerns about the COVID-19 / coronavirus pandemic 2020, people in all the countries are having the more or less similar kind of worries the following are the data collected for the countries like, China, Germany, United Kingdom, United States as the effect of the COVID-19 was more.

- My family's health
My country's economic stability

- My parent's / older friends health
- My physical health
- My economic situation
- Food shortages
- My country's political stability
- My mental health
- My job security
- Rioting or looting
- Other
- Don't know

The major concern came up, family wellbeing and countries economic stability. People work for family, they earn money for the family to full fill the needs of the family and all the economic activities are related for earning money. If the economic state of the country is stable or can manage the damage that has been done due to the situation the economy can come back to the track, although it will take some time.

The study shows some other factors also, those are also equally important in the current situation.

There has been an effect on the aviation industry due the COVID-19, people are not flying from one location to another for tourism or business purpose, and there has been complete locking due to which there is a negative change in the revenue passenger kilometers in the same.

Fig. 3. Year-on-year change of revenue passenger kilometers (RPKs) in the aviation industry in 2020, by region

The above image shows the change [negative] in the revenue in various major country regions like Asia Pacific, North America, Europe, Middle East etc.

Similar to the situation the freight traffic is also blocked, the following image showing the effected change in the same.

Fig. 4. Worldwide air freight traffic from 2004 to 2020 in [million metric tons]

The following image is showing Airline revenue loss in selected countries affected by coronavirus [COVID-19] in the first half of 2020, by scenario [in billions of U.S. dollars]

Fig. 5. Airline revenue loss in selected countries affected by coronavirus [COVID-19] in the first half of 2020, by scenario [in billions of U.S. dollars]

The major loss in almost each and every part of the economy on the countries who has more effect of corona virus. Mostly Italy, China, America and others.

COVID-19's impact estimate on passenger revenue of airlines by region 2020 - Given that the novel coronavirus (COVID-19) outbreak intensifies, annual estimates for the aviation industry adjusts itself. As of March 2, 2020, annual passenger revenue in the Asia Pacific region was forecasted to decline by approximately 57.3 billion U.S. dollars. As of March 24, 2020, annual passenger revenue of airlines in the region is now estimated to decline by roughly 88 billion U.S. dollars because of the virus. [1]

Fig. 6. Passenger revenue change of airlines due to coronavirus outbreak worldwide in 2020, by region of airline registration (in billion U.S. dollars)*

The following image is showing the loss in sports activities. The sports activities in major countries like Basketball, The Olympics, Soccer, Formula One, Cricket etc. each event generates a lot of money and there has been a lot of money involved in the organizing the activity.

Due to lockdown, there has been no events in following next few months and many of the events are postponed to the next dates, but there are some events which cannot be shifted those are cancelled due to the lack of the audiences.

Not only ticketing the rights of telecast to the satellite channels, advertising revenue and tourism and related activities like transportations like taxi and hotel/ restaurant sector share the loss.

Fig. 7. Estimated loss on Sports activities in million USD

The following image gives the idea of number of cases of corona virus, there has been a constant increase in the graph worldwide day by day from January 8 to April 11, 2020. The situation is getting worse day by day as the spreading of the virus is from person to person even through cough and sneeze in the close proximity of the infected person and on the top of that its effect is detected after few days like after 12 to 14 days before that the infected person himself/ herself doesn't know that he/ she is affected.

The most affected countries are like Italy, America etc., are making their efforts to stop the virus spreading and maintaining the economy by doing business activities from home, employees are working from home to maintain the workflow and handling customers. But the other countries like India and its surrounding there is more danger first the population size is large and people live in the close proximity of each other. There

is a continuous process of research and development in making the vaccine of the corona virus but till date there is no success, this creates a more havoc and disturbance in the psychology of people more of uncertainty and loss of life.

Fig. 8. Number of cumulative cases of coronavirus (COVID-19) worldwide from January 8 to April 11, 2020, by day

Share price index in major developed and emerging economies from March 2019 to March 2020, showing a decline in the graph.

Till Dec 2019 the graph shows growth and stability as per the changes of market factors the major countries like European, India, Japan, Russia, United Kingdom, and United States etc. All developed and developing countries market are effected as all the business activities are stopped or slowed down due to effect of COVID -19.

There is clear decline in the graph in the month of Feb and Mar 2020. Whole world is effected and this effect will last till the year end, this is a major correction phase in the share market sector.

The yellow line in the graph is showing the Indian market, there has been effect all over the world but the major decline can be seen in the markets of United Kingdom and United States.

Fig. 9. Share price index in major developed and emerging economies from March 2019 to March 2020

Forecasted change in revenue from the travel and tourism industry due to the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic worldwide from 2019 to 2020(in million U.S. dollars)

Fig. 10. Forecasted change in revenue from the travel and tourism industry due to the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic worldwide from 2019 to 2020(in million U.S. dollars)
Source - <https://www.statista.com>

According to the Mobility Market Outlook on COVID-19, the global revenue for the travel and tourism industry will be an estimated 568.6 billion U.S. dollars in 2020 - a decrease of around 17 percent from the previous year. Additionally, this is significantly lower than the original 2020 forecast of around 712 billion dollars. [2]

Following the trends in the decline of world economy, the Indian economy is not untouched, India is one of the biggest market in the world and in terms of population too. People are involved into trading practices, import – export of finished and unfinished goods to the all over the world, many multinational companies are doing business in the market, suddenly restricting millions of people from coming out from home results into the stopping the trading and other business activities although there are some activities which are being done online but all cannot be done as the economy is based on agriculture and other activities in which there is a must involvement of people.

Due to which, there is an estimation of impact from the coronavirus (COVID-19) on India's GDP growth in 2020.

Fig. 11. Impact of the coronavirus (COVID-19) on India's GDP growth in 2020

India's GDP growth was cut to 2.5 percent from 4.5 percent for calendar year 2020 due to the estimated impact of the coronavirus (COVID-19). The country went into lockdown on March 25, 2020, the largest in the world, restricting 1.3 billion people. [3]

The country went into lockdown on March 25, 2020, the largest in the world, restricting 1.3 billion people the lockdown is going on all over the India and in many parts there is situation of curfew where the damage is more or there is possibility of more damage in the areas where the population is dense and people live in close proximity.

The following data is showing the deaths caused by COVID - 19 in India and worldwide till Apr 12, 2020. The situation is tensed as the infection is passed from person to person and the people living in close proximity are in danger zones.

Fig. 12. Number of novel coronavirus (COVID-19) deaths worldwide as of April 12, 2020, by country

There has been impact on the purchasing behaviors of people in India due to lockdown, people are purchasing the necessary goods a bit more in the anticipation of the shortage of goods as the result there is a rise in price and shortage of goods.

The following image shows the impact of corona virus on purchasing the essential goods in India. The data shown in the following image is of 30 mar 2020, where the impact and anxiety was stated going to grow in the public at this time people are just picking the items as precautions some things are getting in an easy way some are not available due to stocking or over purchasing by people.

Fig. 13. Opinion about the coronavirus (COVID-19) lockdown impact on purchasing essential goods in India in March 30, 2020,

In the list of essential items there is one more item that has been added due to the effect of corona virus, “hand sanitizer”. In normal conditions people do not purchase hand sanitizer on daily basis the shopkeepers also don’t stock much of that but due to the impact of virus, there has been sudden scarcity of hand sanitizer in the market and if available people are asking for “premium” prices.

After that there has been some control by the government in restricting the “premium” prices of **hand sanitizer**. The following image shows that 64% people have brought at “**higher price**” as mandated by the government. 26% people says that they have purchased at the mandate price of government and 10% purchased at the higher price from “online” shopping.

Still the hand sanitizer is not very easily available but the prices are somewhat under controlled, not as the month of March, 2020.

Fig. 14. Opinion about the coronavirus (COVID-19) lockdown impact on hand sanitizer pricing across India as of March 31, 2020

Opinion on the impact of COVID-19 on business India 2020 on statista.

According to a survey conducted to understand the impact of the coronavirus COVID-19 on Indian startups and SMEs, a majority of respondents stated that it would have an impact. About 30 percent of respondents felt that it would decrease demand for their products or services. [4]

Fig. 15. Views of people on imbalance in the demand and supply of goods during lockdown.

The country went into lockdown on March 25, 2020, the largest in the world, restricting 1.3 billion people into their homes resulting into disturbance in the supply chain of the business and imbalance in the demand and supply of goods.

The above image shows the views of people on the impact, majority of people are saying that there would be increase in the supply cost as well as there would be decreased in the demand of the goods.

The estimated economic impact from the coronavirus (COVID-19) on India in 2020, by sector GVA (in billion Indian rupees)

Finance and real estate, with the exception of banking healthcare services was projected to take on a large part of the disruption caused by the coronavirus epidemic in India as of March 2020. The overall impact of COVID-19 on the country's economy was estimated to reach nearly 8.8 trillion Indian rupees. Even though GDP forecasts cut growth for the south-Asian country, the large unorganized sectors of the country were said to keep the economy from collapsing.

Fig. 16. Estimated economic impact from the coronavirus (COVID-19) on India in 2020, by sector GVA (in billion Indian rupees)

<https://www.statista.com/statistics/1098456/india-impact-of-coronavirus-on-business/>

Other than finance and real estate there are other sector which are having impact like Trading, Hotel, Transport, manufacturing, construction, mining etc. the major effect is on those sector where there is a public dealing and there is no interactions between people due to secure closure resulting into loss in billion Indian rupees.

Opinion on impact of the coronavirus (COVID-19) on business cash flow across India as of March 2020 [6]

According to a survey conducted to understand the impact of the coronavirus (COVID-19) on Indian businesses, **about 81 percent reported a decrease in cash flow at their organizations**. Survey respondents included members belonging to Indian private and public corporate sectors and multinational companies.

Since there is no or very less business activities going on from last few weeks, there is support of online working from home but that is not sufficient to bring the cash flow to its original position.

Fig. 17. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1106061/india-impact-of-coronavirus-on-cash-flow/>

Opinion on schools remaining closed through April and May due to the coronavirus (COVID-19) outbreak across India in March 2020. [6]

According to a survey among Indian parents in March 2020, a majority of respondents favored schools remaining closed for two months until end of May. Over 81 percent of respondents wanted schools to reopen on June 1, 2020. Many Indian families that considered the novel coronavirus a health issue stated that they are staying alert and taking precautionary measures.

Fig. 18. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1106364/india-impact-of-novel-coronavirus-outbreak-on-schools-remaining-closed/>

The schools are now closed, but there could be chances of having low attendances of student after opening of schools. As the parents may be concerned due to high impact of the corona virus in world as well as in India.

COVID-19: home office and work-life balance of marketers in the UK in 2020 [7]

Due the spread of coronavirus (COVID-19), many marketing organizations in the UK may have to start operating remotely in 2020. A survey published in mid-March revealed that 73 percent of marketers believe that they are more efficient when working remotely and 68 percent believe that they work more hours at home. Yet just a quarter believe that doing home office will intrude on their personal life.

Impact of home office on the work – life balance of marketers during the corona virus pandemic in the United Kingdom in 2020

Fig. 19. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1104762/coronavirus-home-office-and-work-life-balance-of-uk-marketers/>

Have you started working from home because of the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic? The survey conducted at statista to know that people are working from home due to corona virus effect.

Fig. 20. Have you started working from home because of the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic?

Around 76% people are working from home, 12% saying that they have no impact and 8% are working more than before. Out of more than 1400 respondents. According to the given data people are bound to work from home. There are many sectors of the industry where people are somehow managing the work from home, computer and Information technology are somewhat at comfort level in comparison to others like hotel/restaurant and tourism sectors where it is not possible, here the face to face interaction with customers are needed.

Working from home, giving support from online platform is not very easy at office there are all types of support like from co-workers, IT staff, the speed of Internet and other online security measures. Many staff members are not well equipped due to various reasons like lacking technical background and age factor.

There are some checklist to get started from work from home for corporations/ companies like they have to decide which roles can be remotely handled and train employees' quickly on dos and don'ts of remote access of data keeping in mind all the security measures. Companies have to set out a plan of action involving senior managers/section heads. This should be followed by all members of company. They have to ensure infrastructure is available to all working from home like laptops, software, login credentials, company data to be accessed remotely although it has some security issues such as breach of data as home network is not safe as office network.

Similarly, the employees also have to understand the gravity of the current situation like they must have a clear understanding of productivity goals. They have to set a time table for work and personal commitments, balancing the "work" and "family needs" together also explain to family that you have deadlines and you are not on vacation it's a serious situation all over the world.

To understand the seriousness of the situation that all employees have to work for the common goal and be safe and work from home.

The following data of India as of Apr 13, 2020. The present situation is not promising and it will go to worse condition according to the characteristics of the virus spreading and the time to identify the infected person.

The states of India where the population is densely packed and the nearby areas of cities where the medical facilities are not enough to take care of the situation the score can go high as shown till date. Delhi, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu are already having more than thousand cases reported, Rajasthan and Madhya Pradesh are following the trail.

The author is trying to provide the latest data from the various resources, but there are some limitation in that like the submission and publication deadlines of the article but it's clear from the data available from world and India it's not a good situation.

COVID-19 TRACKER INDIA

	Total cases	Total deaths	Total cured
	9352	324	980
Name of State / UT	No. of cases	Deaths	Cured
Andaman and Nicobar Islands	11	0	10
Andhra Pradesh	432	7	11
Arunachal Pradesh	1	0	0
Assam	31	1	0
Bihar	64	1	26
Chandigarh	21	0	7
Chhattisgarh	31	0	10
Delhi	1176	24	27
Goa	7	0	5
Gujarat	539	26	47
Haryana	185	3	29
Himachal Pradesh	32	1	13
Jammu and Kashmir	245	4	6
Jharkhand	19	2	0
Karnataka	247	6	59
Kerala	384	3	179
Ladakh	15	0	10

Madhya Pradesh	604	43	44
Maharashtra	1985	149	217
Manipur	2	0	1
Mizoram	1	0	0
Nagaland	1	0	0
Odisha	54	1	12
Pondicherry	7	0	1
Punjab	167	11	14
Rajasthan	804	3	21
Tamil Nadu	1075	11	50
Telangana	572	16	100
Tripura	2	0	0
Uttarakhand	35	0	5
Uttar Pradesh	451	5	47
West Bengal	152	7	29
Total	9352	324	980
Data source: Ministry of Health and Family Welfare			
Last updated: April 13 (at 05:50 pm)			

Table 2. Showing the data of Total cases, total death and cured from COVID-19 till Apr 13, 2020.

III. THE IMPACT OF COVID-19 AND INDIAN ECONOMY AND MARKET

Coronavirus outbreak was first reported in Wuhan, China on 31 December, 2019. We can't ignore the fact that the outbreak of COVID-19 in China is expected to have a significant impact on the economy globally including economic slowdown, trade, supply chain disruption, commodities, and logistics.

The GDP of China is expected to decelerate by 1-1.25 percentage points over 2020 because of less production. In China, various cities and provinces are in lockdown mode. China accounts for approximately 19.71% of global GDP at purchasing power parity and obviously it will impact the economy globally. Therefore, it is estimated that the global GDP will suffer an impact of around - 0.5%.

In terms of trade, China is the world's largest exporter and second-largest importer. It accounts for 13% of world exports and 11% of world imports. The lockdown will affect around 500 million people in the country that will deeply impact its consumption of goods.

Impact of Coronavirus on the Indian Economy - Up to a large extent, it will impact the Indian industry. **In imports**, the dependence of India on China is huge. Of the top 20 products

(at the two-digit of HS Code) that India imports from the world, China accounts for a significant share in most of them. India's total **electronic imports** account for 45% of China. Around one-third of machinery and almost two-fifths of **organic chemicals** that India purchases from the world come from China? For automotive parts and fertilizers China's share in India's import is more than 25%. Around 65 to 70% of active **pharmaceutical** ingredients and around 90% of certain **mobile phones** come from China to India. Therefore, we can say that due to the current outbreak of coronavirus in China, the import dependence on China will have a significant impact on the **Indian industry**.

China's share in total imports to India	
Organic chemicals	37%
Inorganic chemicals	13%
Medicinal & Pharma products	36%
Dyes	28%

Source: <https://commerce.gov.in>

Fig. 21. Showing the China's share in total imports to India.

In terms of export, China is India's 3rd largest export partner and accounts for around 5% share. The impact may result in the following sectors namely organic chemicals, plastics, fish products, cotton, ores, etc.

We also can't ignore that most of the Indian companies are located in the eastern part of China. In China, about 72% of companies in India are located in cities like Shanghai, Beijing, provinces of Guangdong, Jiangsu, and Shandong. In various sectors, these companies work including Industrial manufacturing, manufacturing services, IT and BPO, Logistics, Chemicals, Airlines, and tourism.

It has been seen that some sectors of India have been impacted by the outbreak of coronavirus in China including shipping, pharmaceuticals, automobiles, mobiles, electronics, textiles, etc. Also, a **supply chain** may affect some disruptions associates with industries and markets. **Overall, the impact of coronavirus in the industry is moderate.**

According to CLSA report, pharmaceuticals, chemicals, and electronics businesses may face supply-chain issues and prices will go up by 10 percent. The report also says that India could also be a beneficiary of positive flows since it appears to be the least-impacted market. Some commodities like metals, upstream and downstream oil companies, could witness the impact of lower global demand impacting commodity prices. According to CII, GDP could fall below 5% in FY 2021 if policy action is not taken urgently. It is said that the government should take some strong fiscal stimulus to the extent of 1% of GDP to the poor, which would help them financially and also manage consumer demand.

In the third quarter (October-December) growth is slowed down to 4.7% and the impact of COVID-19 will further be seen in the fourth quarter. FICCI survey showed 53% of Indian businesses

have indicated a marked impact of COVID-19 on business operations. And 42% of the respondents said that up to three months could take for normalcy to return.

Sector-wise impact on Indian industry

Chemical Industry: Some chemical plants have been shut down in China. So there will be restrictions on shipments/logistics. It was found that 20% of the production has been impacted due to the disruption in raw material supply. China is a major supplier of Indigo that is required for denim. Business in India is likely to get affected so people securing their supplies. However, it is an opportunity. US and EU will try and diversify their markets. Some of the business can be diverted to India which can also be taken as an advantage.

Shipping Industry: Coronavirus outbreak has impacted the business of cargo movement service providers. As per the sources, per day per vessel has declined by more than 75-80% in dry bulk trade.

Auto Industry: Its impact on Indian companies will vary and depend upon the extent of the business with China. China's business no doubt is affected. However, current levels of the inventory seem to be sufficient for the Indian industry. If the shutdown in China continues then it is expected to result in an 8-10% contraction of Indian auto manufacturing in 2020.

Pharmaceuticals Industry: Despite being one of the top formulations of drug exporters in the world, the pharma industry of India relies heavily on import as of bulk drugs. Due to the coronavirus outbreak, it will also be impacted.

Textiles Industry: Due to coronavirus outbreak, several garments/textile factories in China have halted operations that in turn affecting the exports of fabric, yarn and other raw materials from India.

Solar Power Sector: Indian developers may face some shortfall of raw materials needed in solar panels/cells and limited stocks from China.

Electronics Industry: The major supplier is China in electronics being a final product or raw material used in the electronic industry. India's electronic industry may face supply disruptions, production, reduction impact on product prices due to heavy dependence on electronics component supply directly or indirectly and local manufacturing.

IT Industry: The New Year holidays in China has been extended due to coronavirus outbreak that adversely impacted the revenue and growth of Indian IT companies.

Tourism and Aviation: Due to the coronavirus outbreak, the inflow of tourists from China and from other East Asian regions to India will lose that will impact the tourism sector and revenue.

According to KPMG, the lockdown in India will have a sizeable impact on the economy mainly on consumption which is the biggest component of GDP.

Reduction in the urban transaction can lead to a steep fall in the consumption of non-essential goods. It can be severe if disruption causes by the 21-day lockdown and affect the availability of essential commodities.

Due to weak domestic consumption and consumer sentiment, there can be a delay in investment which further add pressure on the growth. We can't ignore that post-COVID-19, some economies are expected to adopt de-risking strategies and shift their manufacturing bases from China. This can create opportunities for India. According to KPMG, opportunities will largely depend on how quickly the economy recovers and the pace at which the supply chain issues are addressed.

KPMG India Chairman and CEO Arun M Kumar said: "Apart from providing robust safety nets for the vulnerable, a focus on ensuring job continuity and job creation will be imperative". "And there is urgent need to mobilize resources to stimulate the economy for increased demand and employment". According to the KPMG report "It is expected that the course of economic recovery in India will be smoother and faster than that of many other advanced countries".

An outbreak of COVID-19 impacted the whole world and has been felt across industries. World's second-largest economy China became standstill. Its outbreak is declared as a national emergency by the World Health Organization. In India the three major contributors to GDP namely private consumption, investment and external trade will all get affected. World and Indian economy are attempting to mitigate the health risks of COVID-19 with the economic risks and necessary measures need will be taken to improve it. [8]

Indian economy on slippery slope - The growth numbers for the Indian economy were quite bleak even before the outbreak of Covid-19. The Central Statistics Office (CSO) had estimated a nominal growth rate of 7.5 per cent for FY20, the lowest in the last 17 years.

- Manufacturing activity has been in a structural decline for many years and growth in private consumption had collapsed in the aftermath of the IL&FS crisis.
- Lack of government capital spending in FY20 had made gross fixed capital formation crumble as well in FY20.
- The 21-day lockdown, along with the extended impact on travel, hospitality and non-discretionary consumer spends, is expected to deal a major blow to growth in FY21.
- According to SBI's Ecwrap, there is likely to be a 1.7 per cent impact on real GDP in FY21 due to the lockdown, which has brought at least 70 per cent of the economy to a standstill.

- The total cost of the lockdown is estimated at least at 8.03-lakh crore in nominal terms; translating roughly to 4 per cent of GDP.
- Many measures have been taken to reduce economic and social distress. The RBI has cut its policy rate by 75 basis points, and provided additional liquidity through TLTRO (targeted long-term refinancing operation), increasing marginal standing facility and cutting cash reserve ratio. The three-month moratorium on all term loans and working capital is expected to ease the burden on retail borrowers and smaller businesses. The Central and State governments' provision of rice, pulses and cash hand-outs may also provide marginal relief to the needy.
- But the trouble is that the Centre will be facing a double trouble in FY21 — falling tax and divestment revenue, and the need for higher expenditure to tackle the crisis. While the fall in crude prices provides some relief, it will be nullified by foreign portfolio and FDI outflows. These will pressure the rupee, resulting in depletion of forex reserves.
- It is, therefore, not surprising that most economic research outfits have revised India's GDP growth for FY21 sharply lower. SBI economic research pegs FY21 GDP estimate at 2.6 per cent, with a clear downward bias.
- It expects contraction in the GDP of June 2020 quarter, and has revised the FY20 GDP lower from 5 per cent to 4.5 per cent.
- UBS expects India's growth to slow to 2.5 per cent in FY21. The growth is expected to be 4 per cent in the optimistic scenario — if the disruption is contained in mid-May — but the lower range for growth is -0.2 per cent, which can happen if the interruption extends to September.
- CRISIL has slashed the base-case GDP growth forecast for FY21 to 3.5 per cent from the 5.2 per cent expected earlier. This assumes a normal monsoon and the effect of the pandemic subsiding materially in the June quarter. Many other economists have projected growth for FY21 between 2 per cent and 4 per cent.
- It needs to be remembered that we are still in the lockdown period and there is uncertainty over how long the movement restrictions will continue. These forecasts are likely to be revised over the coming weeks and months as the pandemic peaks and finally tapers down. What is clear at this point is that the June 2020 quarter will see economic output shrink very sharply. If the virus is not contained in the June quarter, we could be staring at GDP contraction in FY21.
- The Sensex and the Nifty 50 lost over 35 per cent from their February peaks when the indices hit their recent lows. This sharp decline has helped bring down valuation of large-cap companies to extremely interesting levels.

- The trailing 12-month PE multiple of the Sensex has declined from 27.9 towards the end of December 2019 to 17.18 now. The price-to-book value ratio has declined from 3.21 to 2.19.
 - For the Nifty 50, the price earning multiple corrected from 28.3 to 18.6 and the PB ratio fell from 3.75 to 2.35.
 - Valuations of many large-cap companies have also moved down to very attractive levels, well below their three-year average price-earnings multiples.
 - There are, however, two factors that weigh on near-term appreciation in stock prices. One, revenue and earnings growth in the June quarter is going to contract for most businesses and the overall growth for companies is also likely to be much lower for FY21. According to UNCTAD, profit guidance from multinationals in developing countries have been revised downwards by 20 per cent since the start of the pandemic. Many research reports also point to a downward revision of around 20 per cent in FY21 earnings. India Inc., which was already struggling with poor earnings growth in recent quarters, is likely to be further hit by the slowdown due to Covid-19. Two, the decline in stock prices has been led by foreign portfolio investors, who are pulling money out of all emerging markets due to growing risk-aversion. These outflows will not abate until the virus is contained. But as explained above, valuations are becoming very attractive now. Instead of focusing on the challenges over the next couple of quarters, investors need to buy low-leveraged companies, backed by sound business models, with a three- to five-year perspective.
 - Sectors hurt by the virus attack - Some stocks and sectors have been badly affected by social distancing and movement restrictions.
- Impacted by social distancing**
- Airline** companies have been battered by investors as flights have been grounded and international borders sealed. While Indigo is down around 30 per cent, Spicejet is down a steeper 58 per cent. The relief from low crude oil prices is going to be offset by the loss in revenue for these companies.
- Leisure travel is likely to reduce considerably for the rest of the year, affecting the hospitality industry. It is not surprising that most hotel stocks are down 40-65 per cent since February 20.
 - Investors, however, seem to be betting that food takeaways will continue, with Jubilant FoodWorks down a lower 26 per cent.
 - Tour operators, restaurants and multiplexes are other segments that are likely to suffer through 2020.
 - As the focus shifts to survival and making do with basics, discretionary spending is going to take a back seat. UBS expects private final consumption growth, which was at a multi-year low of 4.3 per cent in FY20, to fall to 1.4 per cent in FY21.
- According to SBI Ecowrap, income loss due to the lockdown will be to the tune of 1.77-lakh crore and loss in capital income of 1.69-lakh crore. Job losses are also expected in agriculture, trade, transport and hotels. Also, the sharp decline in stock prices has eroded investor wealth equaling 44, 25,000 crore.
 - These are likely to impact discretionary consumption across the board — from automobiles to gems and jewelry and textiles to consumer durables — for FY21.
 - Global growth is going to slow considerably in 2020. This will hurt demand for crude oil, metals, chemicals, etc. Commodity prices have, on the whole, declined 37 per cent this year, according to UNCTAD.
 - While this is good for user industries, the commodity producers in the listed universe, including oil-and-gas and metal producers are going to be hurt by the decline in international prices.
 - Global trade is also going to take a hit, with global manufacturing exports declining \$50 billion in February alone.
 - Banking and financial institutions have borne the brunt of selling over the past month, with losses averaging at 43 per cent.
 - In addition to earlier problems including slowing credit growth and asset quality concerns, the ongoing lockdown and the moratorium announced by the RBI have created a fresh set of problems.
 - Asset quality is likely to deteriorate in FY21 due to the problems faced by retail, corporate and small businesses. Job losses, pay-cuts and a sharp decline in revenue due to lower customer spends are likely to impair the ability of the borrowers to repay loans, even after the lockdown period.
 - Sectors that are still afloat- Consumer non-discretionary goods manufacturers have been treated more kindly by investors, with companies such as Hindustan Unilever, P&G Hygiene, Dabur and Colgate-Palmolive escaping with milder cuts of less than 15 per cent.
 - Similarly, many pharmaceutical companies such as Cadila, Ajanta Pharma, Ipca Lab and Dr Reddy's Lab have been spared heavy badgering in the ongoing decline.
 - IT stocks are also expected to be less hurt due to their ability to function from remote locations.
- Looking at the facts and information above it became clear that the next few coming months or till the year end the situation

will be tough for the Indian market. Even after the lockdown is over or the virus situation will come under control the after effects of the COVID-19 will be there and it will take some time to recover from the effects. [9]

World trade is depending upon import- export of goods and material, in intimal period people will fear to import the goods due to virus impact and this can cause the decline in the demand and supply chain. From the above text it very clear that we cannot ignore china if we talk about the trading whole world including India is depending upon various finished and unfinished / raw goods on china.

IV. ORGANIZATION BEHAVIOR

Organizational Behavior (OB) can be defined as the understanding, prediction and management of human behavior both individually or in a group that occur within an organization

Organizational behavior is a field of study that is concerned specifically with the actions of people at work. It focuses primarily on two areas, individual behavior and group behavior. Individual behavior includes topics such as attitudes, personality, perception, learning, and motivation.

In an organization, if humans are happy and satisfied, their mood and behavior will be good, which in turn leads to better productivity or quality of their work. To achieve this goal organizations are constantly working on it, how to get satisfied employees in an organization that ultimately increase the profit of an organization.

It is very clear fact that organizations are working for the profits only, that is another thing that the market is unstable and there are losses and profits due to various external factors.

The prime focus is on which that could be controllable, the internal customers [employees] to keep them motivated and satisfied, organizations are providing various motivating factors.

Although many things can affect the choice of an appropriate structure for an organization, the following five factors are the most common: size, life cycle, strategy, environment, and technology.

An organization is a group of people who work together to achieve individual goals or group goals. Individual goals are goals that members within the group aim to achieve, for example earning money, getting respect, fulfilling family needs and so on. The goals for an organization are profit, development of product and promotion, to achieve market leading position.

Organizations exist to offer resources and services. The quality of these goods and services are the result of the behavior and performance of the employees within an organization.

Organizational behavior (OB), is the study of factors that influence the behavior of individuals and groups within organizations and also the way an organization responds to their

environment. The study of organizational behavior provides concepts and theories that help to understand, analyze and describe the behavior within organization and provides tools for making decisions in order to achieve organizational goals.

There are three major factors that affect OB. The working environment being the base for all three factors, they are also known as the determinants of OB. The three determinants are:

- **People**
- **Structure**
- **Technology**

People

An organization consists of people with different traits, personality, skills, qualities, interests, background, beliefs, values and intelligence. In order to maintain a healthy environment, all the employees should be treated equally and be judged according to their work and other aspects that affects the firm.

Organizational Structure

Structure is the layout design of an organization. It is the construction and arrangement of relationships, strategies according to the organizational goal.

Technology

Technology can be defined as the implementation of scientific knowledge for practical usage. It also provides the resources required by the people that affect their work and task performance in the right direction.

In this research paper the author is concentrating on the various factors of Organizational behavior that came into the picture in contemporary scenario of “secure lockdown” due to COVID-19. The employees are “working from home” there are many sectors in which people are working from home, here the author is going to find out the behavioral aspects of the employees. In any organization, people are important assets working at office in time bound duration the working time are fixed and all the required support structure is available at there. But “working from home” is altogether different scenario however, people are working to achieve their target.

There is some uncertainty regarding the situation of “secure lockdown” there is a great loss of millions of dollars, manufacturing and other marketing activities are stopped only essential things are moving. The “support” structure is only based on the “technology” many people are not fully equipped with technological aspects, some are struggling and seeking support from their fellow employees on phone.

Challenges – face by employees while working from home

According to a survey of over 1,100 employees and almost 800 employers by TimesJobs, nearly 60% **organizations do not have a formal work-from-home policy**. Incidentally, 75% employers are not even comfortable with this idea, whereas 90% employees are keen on having such a policy at work.

There are many hindrances when employees are in collaborative projects, managing time, building trust and also security issues. Now they have to work separately from home location.

- **Collaborative project:** Some projects need more collaboration and face-to-face meeting, discussions become crucial for the project success. Telecommuting may be difficult for employees placed in such projects
- **Time management:** Employees working from home should be able to manage their time judiciously and be responsive and available online as required. So, telecommuters must have the qualities of proper time management, understanding of the work and its process, and ability of decision making.
- **Trust Building:** Employees need to make sure that they do not violate the trust that their managers have placed in them. There should be perfect coordination/chemistry with their manager, boss or co-workers. Any lapse in responsibility from the telecommuter can breach the trustworthiness
- **Fear of Proper recognition & Isolation:** As employees are not physically present in the office they may fear that they may not get proper recognition for the work they have done. So, to tackle this situation, a proper communication must be maintained between employees and employers. Also, some employees feel isolated if they work from home for a long duration as they do not meet their teams regularly
- **Infrastructure and Security Issue:** A proper internet connectivity is essential to ensure that there is no disruption in the work process. Also, there are certain confidential company information and it need to be ensured that those are safe and secure and doesn't get disclosed in public. Some customers of IT services companies want employees to be in a secure zone, and this can pose a challenge to telecommuting.
- **You Handle All the Work Alone -** In a conventional company with an organizational structure different tasks are delegated to employees. In a home-based-business, the entrepreneur handles all of these tasks on his or her own. This workload is elevated to an even higher degree if your business gains momentum and grows. All the mundane and repetitive tasks from the administrative to the operational activities are handled solely by you, the home-based-business owner.
- **You Neglect Spending Quality Time with Your Family-** The greater the success of your home based business the greater the amount of time that is required to operate the business. But whether or not your business is successful, the very nature of starting a new business demands relentless dedication. Working up to 20 hours each day is not unfamiliar territory for a new home business owner.

The time you invest in your business will inadvertently result in you neglecting the time spent with your family.

- **Your Home Life Becomes Your Work Life-** If your business is based in an office sometime in the evening you can close the door, go home and leave the work in the office until the next morning. But working from home poses a different scenario altogether. Your home life unwittingly becomes your work life. No matter where you are in your home, the attraction of checking if you made any sales, or sending an email, or discussing projects with your freelancers becomes forceful; and it also becomes difficult to restrain this urge. The term “**workaholic**” takes on a new meaning in your life.
- **Your Family May Begin to Resent You -** A level of anxiety wells up within me whenever I hear of someone who is about to start a home business. I feel a sense of sympathy toward the individual and their family because I know the strain a home business can have on a family. Beside the hectic schedule you will adhere to, you will also encounter immediate family members who do not understand the concept of working from home. Many people cannot relate to the idea of someone who sits at a computer in his/her home and “works”. To them real “work” is when you leave home at a certain time, go to your place of work, and return at a certain time. Your family may believe that work is going out of the house; therefore if you stay at home you are not working. This lack of understanding can stir up a level of resentment that can cause serious family quarrels if it is not addressed timeously.
- **You Will Encounter Constant Distractions -** In the home environment you may have your kids playing around, dogs barking outside, music blasting from the neighbor's house, and many other distractions. These distractions can hamper your ability to concentrate on the job at hand. Often I have witnessed people who sacrificed everything to start a home based business, but failed due to lack of concentration and they are now left feeding themselves from the crumbs of a social security check, and desperately seeking some form of full-time employment.
- **Productivity and performance mismatch -** The TimesJobs study further reveals that 70% employers still believe that productivity gets hampered when employees work from home. Contrary to this, 44% employees feel that work-from-home helps boost productivity. Also, 80% organizations say no to work-from-home as they say that they have no tracking mechanisms to manage workforce who opt for it.
- **Risks outweigh benefits -** While employers do believe that work-from-home has certain benefits, as 40% see its biggest impact in boosting their employer brand, 30% see it as useful in curbing attrition and another 30% find it beneficial in improving employee productivity which is further linked to organizational output and profitability.

- **Roles are not suitable** - Moreover, 25% employers believe that there are many jobs, which are not conducive to work-from-home arrangements and that is a hindrance in creating such a policy. Of these employers, 42% say work-from-home does not work well in IT related areas of work, 40% say it is not practical for logistics, supply chain management and procurement roles, and another 40% find it is not useful in customer service functions.
- Nearly 35% employers feel work-from-home policy is unsuitable for those working in hospitality and related domains, another 35% say this for administrative profiles, 30% feel it does not work well for engineering profile, 25% see it inappropriate for accounting and finance roles. For 10% work-from-home is useless for sales, business development roles and 5% feel it is irrelevant for those working in entertainment, media and journalism segments. [10]

Fig. 21. Showing impact of remote working from home https://www.shrm.org/hr-today/news/all-things-work/Pages/remote-work-has-become-the-new-normal.aspx

The **major technology support** in current scenario is **computer and Internet** through various applications of video conferencing and communication are very helpful in connecting to the clients and customers.

Here are few **popular online video conferencing applications used in these days**. Many corporates and other people are using online video platform for communication, making a virtual office anywhere at home.

There are lots of option for online video applications with some different or some similar features people are used to Google and Whatsapp for making video calls from their mobile devices or computer, but for an organization where the number of people are more and the need is more. There are many companies who are providing some free and some paid features for online meeting.

Following are some applications who are providing support for online meeting –

- **Skype Meet Now**

Fig. 22. Showing Skype Meet Homepage https://www.skype.com/en/free-conference-call/

Generate your free unique link with one click, share it with participants and enjoy unlimited meetings with Skype. Full set of features at your disposal. Your meeting link does not expire and can be used anytime.

- **Cisco Webex**

Fig. 23. Showing Cisco Webex Homepage https://www.webex.com/downloads.html/

Webex is offering you the most secure collaboration platform in the world to help everyone stay safe and connected in these challenging times.

- HD video for face-to-face meetings
- Flexible audio-only conference call options
- Easy screen sharing
- Meet across any device
- One-on-one or group messaging
- Digital two-way white boarding
- Rich content and file sharing
- Video calling
- Try Webex free

• StarLeaf

Fig. 24. Showing StarLeaf Homepage <https://www.starleaf.com/>

Work better, wherever you are. Experts in making remote working work for you. StarLeaf gives you everything you need to keep connected during the coronavirus outbreak.

• Jitsi Meet

Fig. 25. Showing Jitsi Meet Homepage <https://jitsi.org/jitsi-meet/>

More secure, more flexible, and completely free video conferencing. Go ahead, video chat with the whole team. In fact, invite everyone you know. Jitsi Meet is a fully encrypted, 100% open source video conferencing solution that you can use all day, every day, for free — with no account needed.

What else can you do with Jitsi Meet?

- Share your desktop, presentations, and more
- Invite users to a conference via a simple, custom URL
- Edit documents together using Etherpad
- Pick fun meeting URLs for every meeting
- Trade messages and emojis while you video conference, with integrated chat.

• Whereby

Fig. 26. Showing Whereby Homepage <https://whereby.com/>

Freedom to work from anywhere, Enjoy the freedom to live and work where you thrive with easy video meetings from Whereby. Whereby is a flexible tool providing you with video meetings in the browser – no downloads & no logins for guests

• Hangouts

Fig. 27. Showing Google Hangout Homepage and Google PlayStore Page for download <https://hangouts.google.com/>

https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.google.android.talk&referrer=utm_source%3Dlandingpage%26utm_campaign%3Dlandingpage&hl=en-US

Talk to your friends and family, Hangouts lets you video call, phone, or message the people you love.

- Video Call
- Phone Call
- Message

• RemoteHQ

Fig. 28. Showing RemoteHQ Homepage <https://www.remotehq.com/>

Get more done together, Collaboration workspaces for distributed teams. Work together in ways that go beyond video chat. Co-browse and co-edit any web app, share files, take notes, whiteboard, screen share, video chat, and more. All in a single browser tab.

No download required / Try for Free

- Talky

Fig. 29. Showing Talky Homepage
<https://talky.io/>

Truly simple video chat and screen sharing for groups up to 6 people. Talky is the easy way to connect with friends and family. Rather than using a personal account, Talky uses unique URLs that you can share with those you're meeting with. Just create a room and share the URL with your chat partners. All they need to do is navigate to your link with a supported browser to start the chat!

Your browser may ask for permission to use your camera and microphone. You'll need to click "allow" on these prompts to use Talky.

- Highfive

Fig. 30. Showing Highfive Homepage
<https://highfive.com/coronavirus>

Intelligent meeting rooms require a modern approach to video conferencing hardware. With HD video and industry-leading audio powered by Dolby Voice®, Highfive's hardware is purpose-built to deliver an exceptional "like you're there" experience. And setup of any Highfive kit takes less than 15 minutes. Now that's smart!

- 8x8

Fig. 31. Showing 8x8 Homepage
<https://www.8x8.com/>

8x8 Inc. is a provider of Voice over IP products. 8x8 products include cloud-based voice, contact center, video, mobile and unified communications for businesses

- BlueJeans

Fig. 31. Showing BlueJeans Homepage
<https://www.bluejeans.com/>

BlueJeans Network is a company that provides an interoperable cloud-based video conferencing service that connects participants across a wide range of devices and conferencing platforms.

- Slack

Fig. 31. Showing Slack Homepage
<https://slack.com/intl/en-in/>

Work from home, Slack brings the team together, wherever you are.

With all of your communication and tools in one place, remote teams will stay productive no matter where you're working from.

Slack brings the team together, wherever you are. With all of your communication and tools in one place, remote teams will stay productive no matter where you're...

• Microsoft Teams

Fig. 32. Showing Microsoft Team Homepage <https://www.microsoft.com/en-in/microsoft-365/microsoft-teams/group-chat-software>

Microsoft Teams is a unified communication and collaboration platform that combines persistent workplace chat, video meetings, file storage, and application integration.

• Zoom

Fig. 33. Showing Zoom Homepage <https://zoom.us/>

Zoom Video Communications, Inc. is an American communications Technology Company headquartered in San Jose, California. It provides video telephony and online chat services through a cloud-based peer-to-peer software platform and is used for teleconferencing, telecommuting, distance education, and social relations.

• Jami

Fig. 34. Showing Jami Homepage <https://jami.net/#>

Jami is a free and universal communication platform which preserves the user's privacy and freedoms. **Opensource** meeting tools: Jami is a peer to peer text and video chat software for computers and phones, available as a free download.

• Lifesize

Fig. 35. Showing lifesize Homepage <https://www.lifesize.com/>

Lifesize is a video and audio telecommunications company in the United States which provides high definition videoconferencing endpoints and accessories, touchscreen conference room phones and a cloud-based video collaboration platform.

• FreeConferenceCall.com

Fig. 36. Showing freeconferencecall Homepage <https://www.freeconferencecall.com/global/in>

Get a Free Account - Sign up with just an email and password. Within seconds, receive your account information including dial-in number and access code.

Invite Participants - Provide participants with your dial-in number and access code plus the date and time of the call.

Start Audio Conferencing - At the time of your conference, all participants call their in-country dial-in number followed by the host's access code.

There are lots of option available to support employees and employer to do business activities/ meetings online while staying at home. Many new people/ organization are using for the first time, most of them are not well equipped with all the technological aspects, but the option are available.

V. HUMAN NATURE IN THE “SECURE LOCKDOWN” CONDITIONS

The “nature” of human being is different in different scenario, people are waiting for “Sundays” and “long weekends” in normal conditions and in today’s scenario people are at home, but in this environment a silent stress is going on and there is a pressure of “targets” and “work”.

Many organizations are already providing the flexibility to work from home in many countries, there people are working from their “homes” in normal conditions it works as incentive for them, but the “same” working conditions are in today’s scenario is stressful. The “stress” and “views” could be different for different people like the vies could be different for “female” employees as they have to manage and balance “work” and “home and children” simultaneously, the view of “single” could be something else.

In current research work the author is trying to find out the various aspects of “human nature” when they are bound to “work from home” due to “secure lockdown”, for this the author is going to float a series of questionnaire to understand the “human nature”.

VI. SURVEY QUESTIONS

The following are the series of floated questionnaires to understand the “human nature” in the “secure lockdown” conditions.

The questionnaire are floated through various social platform available such as “Whatsapp” “Facebook” etc. where people are socially connected to get the latest news updates.

1. Kindly select the appropriate Age Group
 - 25-30 Years
 - 31-35 Years
 - 36 – 40 Years
 - 40+ Years
2. Kindly select the Gender
 - Male
 - Female
3. Kindly select the Marital Status
 - Married
 - Single
4. Kindly mention the status of Children(s), if Married, if the status is “single” then kindly choose “None- unmarried” in option.
 - Toddler [Preschooler]
 - Minor [05 to 10 yrs.]
 - Teenage [11- 16 yrs.]
 - Adult [18+ yrs.]
 - None - Unmarried
5. According to you, did you have any experience of “work Flexibility” or “Work from Home” earlier?
 - Never
 - Less than 1 day in a Month
 - Less than 1 day in a Week
 - 1 day in a Week
 - More than 1 day in a Week/ Month

6. According to you, kindly mention the size of company in terms of number of working employees approximately
 - Less than 20
 - In Between 20 – 200
 - In Between 201 – 1000
 - More than 1000
7. According to you, do you think “Work from Home” should be made compulsory once in month for employees to get used to it and prepare for future “similia” circumstances
 - Yes
 - No
8. Kindly mention, the Industry / Sector in which you work for irrespective of your post or position
 - Apparel and textiles
 - Auto and auto components
 - Building and construction
 - Chemicals and petrochemicals
 - Internet business
 - Financial services
 - Banking and NBFCs
 - Food and agriculture
 - Metals and mining
 - MSMEs
 - Pharmaceuticals
 - Power
 - Transport and logistics
 - Hotel and Restaurants
 - Tourism
 - Automobiles
 - Aviation
 - Education and Higher Education includes School and Colleges
 - Tuition and Coaching Classes
 - Transport and Bus Travel
 - Railways
 - Hospital
 - Sports and Sporting Events
 - Entertainment includes Parks Cinema etc.
 - Consumer and Shopping Malls
 - Retail Sector
 - Financial Services like Stocks, Mutual Funds
 - Insurance
 - Telecom/ Manufacturing
 - Shipping – Air Cargo, Sea Cargo
 - Oil and Gas Production
9. In the current Scenario of “Secure Closure” and “Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home” Situation. According to you, do you think that employee gets flexible work environment where employees decides own working hours.
 - Yes
 - Mostly
 - Very less as assignments and Meeting are there
 - No
10. In the current Scenario of “Secure Closure” and “Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home” Situation. According to you, do you think that employee get a “relaxed” home environment to work.
 - Yes
 - No
11. In the current Scenario of “Secure Closure” and “Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home” Situation. According to you, do you think that employee get closeness of home and family members and it helps a lot.
 - Yes
 - No
12. In the current Scenario of “Secure Closure” and “Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home” Situation. According to you, do you think that employee “saves” fuel, Time of travelling while working from home?
 - Yes
 - No
13. In the current Scenario of “Secure Closure” and “Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home” Situation. According to you, do you think that employee get an increase in productivity and creativity?
 - Yes
 - No

- Yes
 No
14. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that employee gets some difficulty in balancing the load of "office work" and "home and family obligations?"
- Yes
 No
15. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that employee get involved "intentionally" in working pressure.
- Yes
 No
16. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that employee works "endlessly" to finish the work or to prepare for the next day as all 24 hours are available at the disposal, not usual typical "office hours".
- Yes
 No
17. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that employee get or can get some health issues due to prolonged working, less or no mobility like Eye Stress, Head Ache, Back Problem, Obesity, Anxiety etc.
- Yes
 No
18. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that all or most of the employees are technical well equipped or having technical education background to manage the situation.
- Yes
 No
 Support is needed
19. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that employee get all the technical facilities at home like Computer/ Laptop, Fax, High Speed Internet, Printer, UPS etc.
- Yes
 No
 Most of them but not ideal office setup
20. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that online meeting with clients/ customer while closing the marketing and sales deals solve the purpose?
- Yes
 No
 In some cases Face to Face meeting is must
 Online meeting is only an alternative not replacement
21. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that the volume of work seems to be more when you work from home?
- Yes
 No
22. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that employee feels "quarantined" or "not having the feeling of working at office?"
- Yes- very frequently
 No - works comfortably
 Occasionally
23. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that employee "lack/deficits" emotional support from office environment and co-workers?
- Yes- very frequently
 No - works comfortably
 Occasionally
24. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that employees experience "shortages" of informal interactions with office co-workers such as coffee breaks, Lunch Breaks etc.?
- Yes- very frequently
 No - works comfortably
 Occasionally
25. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that this situation the "job" of employees make them feel -?
- Tensed
 Worried
 Uneasy
 Relaxed
 Calm
26. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that ?
- I feel emotionally drained from "work/ working at home"
 I feel "used up" at the end of the day
 I feel "worn out" and "tired"
 I feel "not resting properly"
27. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, what is the approx. Time spent "online" while working with co-workers or team in a working day?
- With co-workers or team less than 1 hour
 With co-workers or team between 4 - 5 hours
 With co-workers or team between 5 - 8 hours
 With co-workers or team more than 8 hour
28. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, all the "work" handled by self, in what percentage [%] of "comfort level" do you find yourself in handling client issues, customer satisfaction, IT issues, Customer data, sales/ deal closing etc.
- Up to 25%
 Up to 50%
 Up to 75%
 Up to 100%
29. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that your family needs are neglected as "work time" and "family time" are mixed up?
- Yes
 No
30. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that family members are reflecting some negative reactions/ responses as employees are became "workaholics" or not able to justify "work" & "home needs"?
- Yes
 No
31. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that employees "feels" distractions/ disturbances from family members or pets as all of them are present at employees "work" time?
- Yes
 No
32. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that there could be loss of data or breach in security as home networks are not secure as "office network"?
- Yes
 No
33. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that is an age group of employees who are not very comfortable to IT - Tech/ gazettes as compared to youngsters and they feel outdated or having difficulty in smooth working?
- Yes
 No
34. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that what could be the hurdle in work from home environment?
- Loneliness
 Collaborating and communicating with customers and co-workers
 Distractions at home
 Adjusting time zones with clients/ customers
 Staying motivated
 Taking breaks while working
 Speed of Internet
 Others
35. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that this situation can cause "adverse effect" on Indian economy resulting into loss of millions of dollars?
- Yes
 No
36. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, on an average in past few weeks how often do you communicated with office co-workers for getting assistance or for completion of work?
- Very frequently
 Once or twice
 4-6 times
 One time at least once
37. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, in past few weeks, kindly rate the impact of following factors while working in percentage -
- Not able to access the customer data or records comfortably
 Trouble in online video communication
 Trouble in managing some computer applications
 Difficulty in sending / receiving e-mails or attachments
 Internet speed
 Unable to access the required information from company due to "security" settings
 Other issues
38. In the current Scenario of "Secure Closure" and "Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home" Situation. According to you, do you think that which are the "disturbing" factors for "Female employees"?

- Handling the needs of children(s)
- House hold work
- Preparing food for family
- Laundry
- Time – based work conflict
- Balancing the “work” and “family”
- Behavioral conflicts
- Managing strain/ stress

39. In the current Scenario of “Secure Closure” and “Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home” Situation. According to you, do you think that, “you” should continue to “work from home” if the company permits?

- Yes
- No
- May be depends on the future needs

40. In the current Scenario of “Secure Closure” and “Work Place Flexibility/ Work from Home” Situation. According to you, do you think that you have received “sufficient support” from managerial level/ seniors/ co-workers while completing the “assigned work?” kindly select the level of support as-

- Marginal
- Adequate
- Good
- Very supportive

The number of questions are a bit more than expected at initial screening. Later on to understand all aspects of human nature while working at home the questionnaire a bit extensive to cover most of the feelings. As this was the first time in many decades that people are restricted at home and somehow managing the “work” and “home” responsibilities altogether at one time. Some sectors like banking, police and hospitals are working to handle the crisis this makes another opportunity to get the feelings how they are managing in this situation is another potential area on which research work can be done, maybe at later stage when all this will be under control.

VII ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS

For the analysis and interpretation of the responses collected from various respondents will give the glimpse of what they feel under the crisis situation.

In response to the questionnaire there were many respondents who are facing problems during Secure Closure Situation due to COVID-19 in India. Everyone is on the same page in response to the situation irrespective of level in the organization the workload could be different but the situation of “work from home” is same for each and every respondent.

In response to the question 1, that was about the Age Group of respondents the data received is as under –

Looking at the chat above it seems that the respondents are very evenly distributed in terms of age group. It’s a good sign for the statistical calculation that the primary age group is evenly distributed and their responses are according to it.

In response to the question 2, that was about the Gender of respondents the data received is as under –

It is reflecting the above similarity with the age group the gender is also important factor in the calculation, as for female workers they have to manage the “work” as well as “home” both. The above chart shows almost equal proportion in gender calculation.

In response to the question 3, that was about the Marital Status of respondents the data received is as under –

The graph shows above 70% respondents are married and working from home. Married person has in house responsibilities too in the secure closure situation and working from home creates different situation. There is no office setup, colleagues and limited support although there is a moral support from the family members but it’s altogether a different situation.

Having more than 70% married respondents will give some interesting feedback to the situation.

In response to the question 4, that was about the status of Children(s), if Married, respondents the data received is as under –

The population of children’s is also well distributed 29.4% don’t have children, around 5.8% have preschoolers, 15% are minor and 35.2% are teenagers with 13.7% are adult.

The given data reflect that majority of the respondents are having responsibilities of children's. Working with children's at home is quite difficult there is a lot of disturbance created by their presence and their needs.

In response to the **question 5**, that was about the experience of "work Flexibility" or "**Work from Home**" earlier, respondents the data received is as under –

In India it's very common to work from office not from home. As it is clearly reflected from the above chart that more than 74% population of the respondents are not having the experience of "Work from Home" culture. There are a few respondents who have some prior experience of "Work from Home" but it's very less if we compare the gravity of the situation in today's scenario.

In response to the **question 6**, that was about the **size of company in terms of number of working employees**, respondents the data received is as under –

The data from the above chart shows that 48% of the respondents are in the company with 20-200 employees, 26% of the respondents are in the company with 201-1000 employees, 14% of the respondents are in the company with more than 1000 employees and 12% of the respondents are in the company with less than 20 employees.

Larger the company larger the responsibility and the work, majority of respondents are dropping in the medium to large size of company. Most of the companies in India are dealing with manufacturing and marketing of goods and many people are engaged into it. While there is no physical movement in the market no trading and manufacturing can be done to prevent further infection, people are working from home up to an extent. But where there is need of interaction between man and machine it cannot be ignored. The data gives the author a good glimpse that the views of the respondents will be justified according to the situation.

In response to the **question 7**, that was about the "**Work from Home**" should be made compulsory once in month, respondents the data received is as under –

Looking at the chart above, it's a clear indication from the respondents about the question that work from home should be made compulsory at least once in a month. More than 97% of the population of the respondents are ready to opt this option. According to the situation faced by the employees due to secure closure conditions they "have" to work either with ease or without ease. Many are facing problems as it's not a preferred culture in India. The positive response to this question may be also that in many counties the option of work from home is earned as incentive from the employees that culture could be cultivated here also in all trades, only a few IT sectors are having this.

In response to the **question 8**, that was about the **Industry / Sector in which you work**, respondents the data received is as under –

According to the data received the population of the respondents are coming from almost every sector. The percentage is also more or less identical with slightly more in education sector.

Schools, colleges and coaching centers are closed but this sector doesn't really needs to have physical presence of teachers and students although it's a must requirement but in the current situation only this sector is active which helps the students to get information and knowledge distribution through online mode. Another similar sector is IT and its related services gives online support to its customers. In other sectors of the industry people are working but the impact is less in comparison to the IT and education sector.

In response to the **question 9**, that was about **employee gets flexible work environment**, respondents the data received is as under –

In response to the question about the flexible work environment while working from home, 50.9% of the population of the respondents are agree that they can adjust the working hours, 21.56% they got less flexible time as the assignments are there and when you work in a team you have to adjust your other things according to it. 21.56% they are agreeing clearly to this they are having the flexi time advantage. Only 5.88% are disagreeing to the flexi timings.

The data and the percentage of the respondents clearly shows that majority of the respondents are having the advantage of flexi timings where the employees can adjust working hours, very few but there are people who can't adjust their timings that depends on the industry's sector in which they are working, in some sectors people have to work in time bound conditions either online/offline.

In response to the **question 10**, that was about **employee get a "relaxed" home environment to work**, respondents the data received is as under –

76% of the respondents are agreeing that they have a relaxed environment at home to work. The reflection to this side is may be due to the situation as each person is having attachment to their family members and this infection is spreading form person to person, if the employee can work from home and other people are also at home and safe from any danger this creates the feeling of relaxed and safe working environment. Another reason could be any person is a bit relaxed at their home and the working hours are flexible according to the need.

24% of the employees as respondents are not able to find peace at home may be due to some disturbance and working in the typical sector where the flexi timing are not possible.

In response to the **question 11**, that was about **employee get closeness of home and family members**, respondents the data received is as under –

It is very clear from the responses received from the respondents' closeness to the family members and working at home gives a support and relief from the family tension from the virus infection. 91% of the respondents are agreeing to this. This gives another indication that people working from home are a bit relaxed if this practice can be continued in future as an incentive or by other means when this situation is over that can yield into more efficiency to the work.

In response to the **question 12**, that was about **that employee "saves" fuel, Time of travelling**, respondents the data received is as under –

More than 97% of the respondents are agreeing to this that employees are saving "fuel" and "time of travelling" while working from home, it's a common practice to go to office for

work and almost all employees invest their money in fuel and maintenance of the vehicle also the time invested in travelling that can be used effectively for increased in productivity of employees. This can be exempted in the case of marketing activities and service sector where the movement of the employees is essential but in other sector it can be managed.

In response to the **question 13**, that was about **employee get an increase in productivity and creativity**, respondents the data received is as under –

80.4% of the employees are in support of the fact that there is increase in the productivity and creativity if the employees are working from home. There reasons associated to this could be relaxed environment and family support as well as the flexi timings of working.

In response to the **question 14**, that was about **employee gets some difficulty in balancing the load of “office work” and “home and family obligations**, respondents the data received is as under –

89% of the respondents are supporting to the fact that they are having some problems in balancing the “work” and “home” situation. This may be due to the reasons like the children of the employees as reflected in previous questions mostly needs attention and there are female employees who are definitely facing this issues, as all of the family members are at home and there are many routine works ready for the female employees. 10.8% people from the population of respondents are saying they do not have any trouble, may be the response came from the population who has no children or still unmarried. From

question 3 around 27% are unmarried and from question 4 around 29% are not having any children.

Altogether, people are facing difficulty in balancing the “work” and “home”, another reason could be that this is the first time when people are working from home and most of them do not have any prior experience of the same.

In response to the **question 15**, that was about **employee get involved “intentionally” in working pressure**, respondents the data received is as under –

In the response to this question, 80% of the respondents saying “yes” that they are involving intentionally under working pressure. The possible reason could be the seriousness of the situation and most of the employees are working from home for the first time and they are having difficulties in balancing the situation as it becomes very clear from the question 14 response. 20% of the employees are saying “no” to the question, may be they are having some prior knowledge of working from home and technology well equipped and unmarried.

In response to the **question 16**, that was about **employee works “endlessly” to finish the work or to prepare for the next day as all 24 hours are available**, respondents the data received is as under –

89% of the population of the respondents are agreeing to this that they work endlessly, as there are no office timing restrictions as such and flexible environment feeling boost the intention of completing the work. In normal days people are

working only in office timings if the remaining work other than most important that seek attention due to deadlines is shifted or scheduled to the next working day. Working from home includes all work like with deadlines or normal the intention of clearing the pipeline of pending work or for the preparation makes a greater involvement that also disturbs the work and home balance.

In response to the **question 17**, that was about **employee get or can get some health issues due to prolonged working**, respondents the data received is as under –

In the response to this question, 86% of the respondents are saying “yes” that prolonged working can raise the health issues, from the question 16 it’s clear that employees are having all 24 hours to work and they are engaged in endlessly to finish the work that involves the long working hours and needs continuous sitting, less movement. Due to the secure closure conditions there is absolutely no movement outside the home. This could possible generates health problems for the employees. 13% are not agreeing to this as they are used to the flexi working conditions or they must be associated to the sectors where there are less work pressure.

In response to the **question 18**, that was about **all or most of the employees are technical well equipped**, respondents the data received is as under –

In response to the question, 73.9% population of the respondents are saying that support is needed, 17.3% are saying “no” and 8.69% are in support. The data reflects very clear picture most of the employees are not well equipped with the

technical stuff and there is need of support. This is the crisis time where everyone is in fear and working from home with limited knowledge, a very few handful of people who have complete working knowledge and they can cope up with the situation.

More than 80% population has some difficulty in handling the situation, people coming from different background of education streams and everyone is not very skilled to do the job on its own – support is needed.

In this situation, where you have to do the task and other people are also at the same stage facing the difficulties this creates some tension, sense of insecurity in concern to the job.

In response to the **question 19**, that was about **employee get all the technical facilities at home like Computer/ Laptop**, respondents the data received is as under –

78% of the respondents are saying that they have the technical gazettes like computer / laptop, Printer, Internet etc. but not ideal office setup. 6.522% are saying “no” and around 15% are saying “yes” they have idea setup to work.

Looking at the data chart people are struggling with technical gestates, computer / laptop can be found in most of the homes but the problem is this can the “home computer/ laptop” do the “office” work or the Internet connection speed is at par to do the work comfortably. The usage of technical stuff is again depending upon the previous knowledge of the employees, in normal office days they are having in-house support from IT department but in current situation they are home alone.

In response to the **question 20**, that was about **online meeting with clients/ customer while closing the marketing and sales deals solve the purpose**, respondents the data received is as under –

In response to the question regarding closing the marketing sales calls online. 50% of the respondents are in favor of “In some cases Face to Face meeting is must”, 32% are in favor of

“Online meeting is only an alternative not replacement”, 15% are saying “yes” it do the job, 2.1% are saying “no”.

The possible reason for the above responses could be, this is the first time when people are working from home and meeting online for marketing and sales calls. In normal deals people meet face to face and close the calls, most of the calls are fruitful but as 50% people are saying face to face meeting is a must. 32% says it’s an alternative not replacement, usually people do not do the business in this way, they are having some problem in adopting this new mechanism, but technology cannot fully replace the people interaction. it also depends on the sector in which you are working. Like those 15% respondents who say “yes” must be working in those sectors where online meeting could solve the purpose.

In response to the **question 21**, that was about **the volume of work seems to be more when you work from home**, respondents the data received is as under –

In response to the volume of work from work, 88.3% respondents are in favor and saying “yes” at home the volume of work increased and 11.6% people are saying “no”. the responses clearly indicates that the work load is increased while working from home, as from the **previous questions Q15, Q16** it is reflected that people involved in working more and became workaholics, as they have all the 24 hours to do the work this factor is responsible in increasing the work load it also depends on the sector in which the employee works. “No” from 11% people could be due to the sector specific privilege available to the respondents.

In response to the **question 22**, that was about **employee feels “quarantined” or “not having the feeling of working at office?”**, respondents the data received is as under –

“Yes- very frequently”, 40%, “Occasionally” with 34.091% and “No – works comfortably” with 25.000%.

This is the first time for most of the respondents to work from home and people are facing the feeling of missing the office environment, more than 70% of the respondents are “missing” office feeling frequently or occasionally due to lack of support from the co-workers and facilities of the office not available at home. Although they are a bit relaxed from the family health concern but office environment is not available at home. 25% people are working from home without missing the office environment this may be because of the sectors in which they work for.

In response to the **question 23**, that was about **employee “lack/deficits” emotional support from office environment and co-workers?** Respondents the data received is as under –

“Yes- very frequently”- 45.455%, “Occasionally”- 27.273% and “No – works comfortably”- 27.273%. This is the first time when people are working from home and other co-workers are also at their home, people are missing the office setup environment as it’s very clear from the **previous question**. If the author combines the responses of “yes” and “occasionally” it became more than 60% of the respondents who lack emotional support from their co-workers. Usually people work in collaboration with each other and to complete the work in time with the help of co-workers as a team it’s a common phenomenon can be seen at almost all the work places. With 27% people from the respondents are working without any “missing” it also resembles with the population response from the previous question depending upon the sector specific working.

In response to the **question 24**, that was about **employees experience “shortages” of informal interactions with office co-workers such as coffee breaks, Lunch Breaks etc.?** Respondents the data received is as under –

In response to the “employees experience “shortages” of informal interactions with office co-workers such as coffee breaks, Lunch Breaks etc.” the respondents with “Yes- very frequently- 40.909%”, “Occasionally - 34.091%” and with “No – works comfortably - 25.000%”.

Man is a social animal and interacting while working in team and taking breaks talking informal it’s a routine while working, due to lock down and working from home people are “missing”

the fun at work if the author combines the “yes” and “occasionally” responses it becomes more than 70%, there are some respondents who work from home without missing their informal breaks depends on the work culture and sector of the industry.

In response to the **question 25** that was about **this situation the “job” of employees make them feel –?** Respondents the data received is as under –

The respondents clearly indicates the “feeling” while they work from home, the current situation is very turbulent and uncertain. All over the world lacks of people have died and thousands are infected due to the effect of corona virus and situation is like world is at war from invisible enemy.

People are locked in their homes and working for their living the market is not very supportive, economy is going down in this situation employees are very concern.

The responses received are, Tensed - 36.364%, Worried - 36.364%, Uneasy - 15.909%, Relaxed - 9.091% and Calm - 2.273%. If the author combines the responses “Tenses”, “worried” and “uneasy” that come 89.1% that is a sign of danger people are working under stress condition. Few people also skipped this question due to stress, a 2% of people are mentally strong who are coping are up with the situation.

In response to the **question 26** that was about **According to you, do you think that?** Respondents the data received is as under –

The responses collected to this question what an employee thinks while working from home under lockdown situation. The working at home with all 24 hours are available to plan except the online collaboration with clients and co-workers. The author in this question want to find out the overall feeling of the employee at the end of the day.

I feel emotionally drained from “work/ working at home” - 45.455%, I feel “used up” at the end of the day - 34.091%, I feel “worn out” and “tired” - 13.636% and I feel “not resting properly” - 6.818%. From the data collected from various respondents it’s very clear that everyone is having some issues like 45% are emotionally drained 34% are feeling that they have been used up by the working, some of them are having resting problems.

Flexibility in the work and most of the employees are working from the home are for the first time. These outcomes are may be due to this. People are not used to work like this in home bound conditions with seriousness of the situation outside the home.

Work from home was supposed to be a luxury, an incentive for the employees but here it’s a compulsory evil.

In response to the **question 27** that was about **Time spent “online” while working with co-workers or team in a working day?** Respondents the data received is as under –

The response collected from the respondents for the question to spend time online working with co-workers/ team. The responses are, With co-workers or team less than 1 hour - 53.488%, With co-workers or team between 4 -5 hours - 41.860%, With co-workers or team between 5 -8 hours - 2.326% and With co-workers or team more than 8 hour - 2.326%.

Working in collaboration with co-workers/ team the maximum time altogether is from 1-5 hours as people are facing some technological difficulties as well as some difficulties in getting data from office of customers etc. to get the things done. Collaborating all the work online either customers and co-workers needs online presence and from the data it’s very clear that people are working online for hours in the lockdown period to achieve the given target.

In response to the **question 28** that was about **all the “work” handled by self, in what percentage [%] of “comfort level” do you find yourself in handling client issues customer satisfaction, IT issues, Customer data, sales/ deal closing etc.** Respondents the data received is as under –

In the response to the percentage of comfort level in handling the situation of work from home including cline, IT gazettes etc., as this situation is new for most of the people and the data received from the respondents shows that 69.767% [Up to 75%] are at the comfort level, 11.628% [Up to 100%], 16.279% [Up to 50%] and Up to 25% - 2.326%. Most of the employees are satisfied up to 75% from their working effort followed by 50% and 100%. Looking at the percentage it is a good data to interpret that under the stressed situation of lockdown, working from home employees are able to handle the work, it's a new situation for all the employees from top management level to the lower level. This give an opportunity to convert the rest of the percentage like 25%, 50% to 100% of confidence level so that in future if market faces any condition like this they can handle the situation comfortably.

In response to the **question 29** that was about **do you think that your family needs are neglected as "work time" and "family time" are mixed up?** Respondents the data received is as under –

In response to the question at that the family response is negative due to "work" and "family time" is mixed up to 95.349% are saying "Yes" and "No" are 4.651%. The data clearly shows that people are having trouble in managing the time balance between the "work" and "family". It's a new and

stressed situation for the respondents to handle and sense of insecurity is pushing employees to get the things done. To priority is given to manage the work and family is a bit ignored.

In response to the **question 30** that was about **employees are became "workaholics" or not able to justify "work" "home needs"?** Respondents the data received is as under –

This is an extension to the **previous question** of mixing up the work and home needs and **question 16** that deals with "work endlessly" to finish the work due to the availability of 24 hours. The responses to the current question "Yes" from 88.372% and "No" from 11.628% of employees.

Most of the respondents are new to the technological aspects and there is no doubt that there is a pressure of work on employees. To finish the work and availability of 24 hours to work makes the respondent workaholics.

In response to the **question 31** that was about **employees "feels" distractions/ disturbances from family members or pets as all of them are present at employees "work" time?** Respondents the data received is as under –

In the response to the question of distraction at home, 93.182% of responded are agree and saying "Yes" while the employees who are saying "No" is 6.818%.

Although home environment is a relaxed environment but in present condition the house is full with all the family members

and there are pets too. Present situation is not a normal day situation where you are working from home and other family members are doing their things as per their schedule. This is a tensed situation for all of the family members and they are finding the ways to dissolve their tension or stress like through music or watching movies that could definitely create disturbance while working.

In response to the **question 32** that was about **there could be loss of data or breach in security as home networks are not secure as “office network”** Respondents the data received is as under –

In the response to the question of data breach the responded are clearly supporting with 90.6% the fact that there could be breach in data and 9.32% people disagree from the fact. The higher percentage is of that there could be possibility of data breach from their system.

In office they have robust security measures like firewalls, antivirus and other features which comes in a complete suite. Normally at home people do not invest on heavy / professional security measures as they do not use any sensitive data from home network.

At the present condition this fact could be a serious matter where everything is online and there are many people who can get unwanted advantages from the leaked data.

In response to the **question 33** that was about **age group of employees who are not very comfortable to IT – Tech/ gazettes as compared to youngsters** Respondents the data received is as under –

In the response to the question age group of employees who are not very comfortable to IT – Tech/ gazettes as compared to youngsters, 90.9% of respondents are saying “yes” to the fact that “age” is a big hurdle in working with technical gazettes senior employees can have the difficulties in managing them. In normal days at office all the staff as well as technical people are available to sort out the issue but at home there could be some problems.

In response to the **question 34** that was about **what could be the hurdle in work from home environment?** Respondents the data received is as under –

This question is about the basic hurdles faced by the respondents while working from home. The respondents with 32.558% choose “Collaborating and communicating with customers and co-workers” followed by with 25.581% “Distractions at home”, 20.930% with “Staying motivated” , 9.302% “Speed of Internet” and with 4.651% Loneliness and Adjusting time zones with clients/ customers with 2.326% of respondents concerns with “Taking breaks while working”.

Looking at the responses from the respondents it seems that they are having problems in collaborating and communicating, all things are going on with the support of IT gazettes and employees are coming from different background of education, different sectors and for the first time working alone from home in a turbulent situation. Another concern is “distraction at home” due to lockdown whole family is at home for 24 hours and this could be the source of distraction while working. Another concern in the line of hurdles is staying motivated, working without the office setup and co-workers and finishing the work in collaboration with others in the tensed situation due

to COVID-19 it I quite difficult to stay motivated. Other things like loneliness and taking breaks are there but in minor percentage.

In response to the **question 35** that was about **this situation can cause “adverse effect” on Indian economy resulting into loss of millions of dollars?** Respondents the data received is as under –

95.5% of respondents are in support to the fact that this situation, the effect of COVID-19 lockdown will damage the economy if India. As all the manufacturing and agricultural activities are closed marketing, tourism, sports and entertainment, movement is locked. Market needs people and there are no people in the market this locking situation will certainly cause the damage in dollars to the Indian economy and world.

In response to the **question 36** that was about **average in past few weeks how often do you communicated with office co-workers for getting assistance or for completion of work?** Respondents the data received is as under –

The respondents to the response of this question, on an average communicated, “Once or twice” - 59.091%, “4-6 times” - 20.455%, “Very frequently” - 18.182%, “One time at least once” - 2.273%. The given data shows that people are communicating frequently to solve their problems depending

upon the sector and work assigned the frequency of collaborating differs.

In response to the **question 37** that was about **in past few weeks, kindly rate the impact of following factors while working in percentage** - Respondents the data received is as under –

While working from home people have faced many problems with 48.837% - “Trouble in managing some computer applications”, 27.907% - “Trouble in online video communication”, 11.628% - “Not able to access the customer data or records comfortably”, “Difficulty in sending / receiving e-mails or attachments”, “Internet speed”, “Unable to access the required information from company due to “security” Other issues are there with minor percentage.

The computer application, video communication, customer data are major issues of concern, depending upon the age and the skills along with the first time working from home in the tensed environment causes some problems. Companies security policies, non-availability of customer data, internet speed etc. these are the practical hurdles that respondents have faced during lockdown and work from home.

In response to the **question 38** that was about **that which are the “disturbing” factors for “Female employees”** - Respondents the data received is as under –

For the female employee to manage the “work” and “family” is a tough job. The respondent gives their feedback on the various issues that can be treated as hurdle. “Handling the needs of children(s)” - 83.721%, “House hold work” - 86.047%, Balancing the “work” and “family” - 88.372% “Preparing food for family” - 76.744%, “Time – based work conflict” - 74.419%, Behavioral conflicts - 44.186% , Managing strain / stress - 34.884% followed by Laundry - 30.233%.

Looking at the received data more than 80% issues the respondents thinks that can be the hurdles for female employees are need of children(s), house hold work and maintain balance

followed by food for family. When all family members are at form for whole 24 hours, it is difficult to manage their needs properly along with the office work. Many female employees are facing these issues during the period as this is the first time when whole family and office work is at home at the same time under the turbulence conditions.

In response to the **question 39** that was about **“you” should continue to “work from home” If the company permits? -** Respondents the data received is as under –

Continuing “work from home”, the responses majorly are with same percentage 47.619% “Yes” and “May be depends on the future needs” with 3.846% are saying “No”.

By the time and experience people are ready to work from home as the future need arises. A few people are still refusing the offer.

In response to the **question 40** that was about **“received “sufficient support” from managerial level/ seniors/ co-workers while completing the “assigned work?” kindly select the level of support as? -** Respondents the data received is as under –

The support from the seniors and co-workers in completing the task is ranked as with 60.465%- Good, with 20.930% - Adequate, with 16.279% - Very supportive and with 2.326% - Marginal.

Looking at the data from the responses the support level is “good” as most of the employees are working from home for the first time in the turbulent environment with high sense of insecurity, it’s a good sign for the future prospect that by internal collaboration for all the people who collaborated together and get the job done as a team work. Many of them faced problems in balancing the work and home situations but somehow things are manageable.

VIII CONCLUSIONS

To conclude this paper, it has multi dimensions some needs to be explored further as future research objectives. The two major points in the research paper covered one is economic condition of the world and India second one is the impact of working from home due to corona virus.

This is for the first time that virus effect is all over the world and man is fearing from another man, to prevent the infection to be spread further complete lockdown was proposed. Another thing that occur for the first time that employees are working from home under this lockdown and whole family is there for 24 hours.

In the study there are several things that came up and needs to be keep under watch. Like all the employees should be trained for present situation, they should be upgraded with the basic knowledge of IT gazettes as many of the responded face struggle, train the employees to balance the “work” and “family” under such circumstances, there has been a great loss of business in two – three months worldwide, its again a question for research how much time it take to get normalized and after that how the market are going to recover the losses. The overall conclusion is that employees are somehow managing the “family” and “work” conditions in the tensed situation and waiting for the market stabilization.

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